

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF CAUSALITY IN ENGLISH AND
KARAKALPAK LANGUAGES

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Uzakova Gozzal Rustemovna

The master of Karakalpak State University

The department of comparative linguistics and linguistic translation

Annotation: *The aim of the article is developing pupils' Comparative analysis of Causality in English and Karakalpak languages and giving instruction to young learners different easy ways of translation different kinds of sentences in English and Kazakh languages taken from the works of different authors and various styles.*

Key words: *phraseological unit, metaphorical term, recognisability, memorability, back translation, phraseological terms, categorial feature, integral part, cognitive approach.*

Abstract. *On the basis of we often need to communicate and permanent cooperation between countries in the modern cultural and economical relationships arises necessity in researches in different aspects of languages. Especially it concerns English and Kazakh languages, firstly, we are developing country and we need to learn foreign languages to raise competitive capacity of our people and country. Secondly, our president determined a goal to know three languages, as: Kazakh is our state language, Russian – official language and English – the language of international relations worldwide, that's we should acquire this language in order to be more successful and to have a chance to learn in a modern world.*

And in this respect the actuality of our work is determined by the comparison of difficult syntactical units and establishment of similar and specific characteristics of types of sentences in English and Kazakh languages. The actuality of the research is the comparatively-typological analysis of the sentence in English and Kazakh languages. Comparing and contrasting the types of sentences from theoretical and practical point of view is the actual problem of grammar. The aim of the research is to study the phenomenon of the sentence and reveal similarities and differences in pattern and character of manifestation of a given phenomenon.

1. Introduction: general information about causality

The scientific novelty of the research is that research work was conducted to reveal the similarities and differences of types of sentence in English and Kazakh languages by using comparatively-typological and contrastive methods.

Types of sentence in English and Kazakh languages are researched by using comparative-contrastive analysis and important opinions are given by scientists about their characteristic features, their main types, similarities and differences. Opinions and conclusions told about the types of sentence in syntax are used in this work. Also, it gives opportunity to understand the features of the sentence, peculiarities of its usage.

The results of made analysis about the types of sentence would answer the question what peculiar properties English and Kazakh languages have in some aspects of syntactical system. The results can be taken into account in practice of teaching English as foreign languages and allow teachers and students to use it in their work and their future work in studying English and Kazakh sentences. It will help to understand sentences from theoretical and practical points of view.

The first part of the work considers the theoretical basis of carrying out of theoretical interconnection of grammar and syntax; theoretical interpretation of the term sentences; variations of the phenomenon “sentence” in other languages; conceptions of the sentence; the usage of sentence in English language.

The second part of the work is dedicated to the comparative-contrastive analysis of the sentence; sentences contrasted with English and Kazakh languages; comparison of types of sentences in English and Kazakh languages; comparison of “types of sentences” in English and Kazakh languages.

2. Comparative analysis of Causality in English and Karakalpak languages

So the adverbial modifier of purpose in both contrasted languages is optional for the structure of the sentence. In English language it may be reflected by an infinitive/infinitival phrase or prepositional gerund.

Hence in Karakalpak language it often introduced by the conjunctions *u'shin*(kk) + the infinitive construction or the preposition *sol u'shin* (kk)+noun.

He smiled to her *to show my sympathy*. - *bildiriwu'shin*. (kk)

The adverbial modifier of result, both in English and Karakalpak, refers to an adjective / an adverb accompanied by an adverb of degree (enough, too, sufficiently, so...as). It may be followed in English and Karakalpak by a subordinate object clause. The clanging and crashing were loud enough *to wake the whole castle*. - *X'ammeni woyatiw u'shin*.(kk)

Thus the adverbial modifier of condition in the contrasted languages is usually expressed by a noun / pronoun preceded by a preposition / a prepositional phrase (*but, for, except for, without*) or by a participle / adjective preceded by the

conjunctions *if, unless*. All of them have direct semantic and functional equivalents in Karakalpak. The adverbial modifier of concession in the sentence points to conditions contrary to the action that takes place (or to the state of object/living being) that continues.

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